

INFLUENCE OF TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP ON PERFORMANCE OF THE NATIONAL GOVERNMENT ADMINISTRATION, KENYA

Shadrack M. Mwadime¹, Dr. Muchelule Yusuf²

^{1,2} JOMO KENYATTA UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURE AND TECHNOLOGY

^{1,2} Nairobi, Kenya

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7244461>

Published Date: 26-October-2022

Abstract: Organizational goals are tied to the influence of Leaders on the people who have a stake on the organization. Research previously conducted on organization's sustainable high performance has addressed this concept from a traditional leadership perspective of a single approach like traits, skills or behaviors. The research sought to address the following objectives; Intellectual Stimulation; Inspirational Motivation; Idealized Behaviors; and Individualized Consideration their relationship with performance of the National Government Administration. The research was anchored on the following theories; The Agency theory; Communication theory; Decision theory, and transformational leadership theory. The general objective was to examine the influence of Transformational leadership on performance of the National Government Administration. The specific objectives was to look at how Intellectual Stimulation; Inspirational Motivation; Idealized Behaviors; and Individualized Consideration their relationship with performance of the National Government Administration. A mixed research method was used to provide the researcher with meaningful insights on the topic. The targeted population were the 338 Deputy County Commissioners who are the leaders of this department at Sub-County level, a fairly Senior Management level, and the researcher drew a sample size of 183 officers, from the different geographical regions of the Country, that represents divergent factors or challenges that these senior managers encounter. The study found transformational leadership to significantly influence performance of the National Government Administration. All the independent variable i.e. Intellectual Stimulation; Inspirational Motivation; Idealized Behaviors; and Individualized Consideration had a significant positive relationship with performance of the National Government Administration. The study recommends organization to embrace Transformational leadership to improve performance. Intellectual Stimulation; Inspirational Motivation; Idealized Behaviors; and Individualized Consideration were able to explain 69.1% or variation in performance at the National Government Administration.

Keywords: Inspirational Motivation, Idealized Behaviours, Individualized Consideration, National Government Administration.

I. INTRODUCTION

Organizations that intend to remain relevant in a dynamic world must be able to quickly and effectively adapt to its changing environment [1]. There is a purpose for the existence of every organization and thus these organizations with a strong sense of purpose tend to thrive even in a turbulent environment. Consequently, an organization that desires to be successful, must fully understand the positive and negative factors that influence its survival, both from its internal and external environment. Leadership is a critical part of effective management in the National Government Administration and plays an important role in its performance. Studies on transformational leadership by various authors have sought to provide the link between leader-follower dynamics and superior performance for organizations that face renewal and transformation demands. In addition, behaviours of transformational leaders have been identified as impacting organization performance positively [2].

On 27th August, 2010, following the promulgation of a New Constitution a new Kenya was born. The object was to devolve politics, fiscal and administrative powers from the Central government to the County governments. Article 174 spells out some of the key objectives of the decentralization which includes “promote democratic and accountable exercise of power; to give powers of self-governance to the people and enhance the participation of the people in the exercise of the powers of the State making decisions affecting them, and to facilitate the decentralization of state organs, their functions and services from the capital of Kenya [3]. The need to actualize self-governance is captured in Article 179 of the Constitution of Kenya, 2010 that requires all executive authority at the county level be vested in the County Executive Committee (CEC) under the chairmanship of the elected Governor and his/her deputy. Article 183: Clause 1 (a-d) empowers County governments to implement County Legislation, coordinate and manage County administration and technical departments, and to undertake other functions conferred by the National Legislation. However, it must be noted that under the old Constitution, development programs and coordination of the National Government policies at the local level was undertaken by the Provincial Administration (PA). This Department that operates under the Office of the President supervised all Government Ministries at Provincial, District, Divisional and Locational levels whilst coordinating their programs and policies [4]. The Colonial authorities established the PA as a state instrument whose activities included coordination of government activities at different administrative levels, chairing a number of committees and general representation of Executive Authority at the local level[5].

A. Statement of the Problem

Leadership that helps in creating a healthy environment, where people are motivated to excel in their work, results in improving the performance of the organization dramatically [6]. Therefore, organizations that lack good leadership leads to a poor work environment and the employees tend to exhibit lack of motivation to work, thereby impacting the performance negatively. It should be noted that Leadership is a key process in achieving organizational goals and objectives and heightening organizational performance [7]. Hence, both the Private and Public sector requires good leadership to achieve its goals. However, today’s public sector leaders are being asked to function with fewer resources and continually find new ways to tackle challenges. The Kenya Public Service, just like any other public sector institutions in the world, is experiencing changes brought about by globalization, technology advancement, competition, economic factors and new Government rules and regulation [4]. This calls for a unique way or style of leadership that will match the challenges encountered in the public sector. Thus, the researcher intends to examine effective leadership and the requisite performance with regard to the National Government Administration in Kenya. Despite the dynamics of a changing environment over the years, and the constant calls to abolish the system, the department has evolved and restructured in its role of coordinating the National Government programs and projects. Hence, its survival or continuous existence may benefit from effective leadership. Studies have been carried out on leadership and performance in various sectors. However, there are limited studies that link Transformational leadership and performance of the National Government Administration. Thus, the purpose of this study is to establish the influence of Transformational Leadership on the performance of National Government Administration.

B. General Objectives

The general objective of the study was to examine the influence of Transformational leadership on performance of the National Government Administration.

Specific Objectives

The study was guided by the following objectives:

- i. To examine the influence of Intellectual Stimulation on the performance of the National Government Administration.
- ii. To establish the influence of Idealized Behaviors on the performance of National Government Administration
- iii. To determine the influence Individualized Consideration on the performance of the National Government Administration.

II. THEORETICAL REVIEW

Transformational leadership Theory

The theory was developed by Burns in 1978. [8] in discussing the theory of transformational leadership in terms of how a leader gets followers to trust admire and respect them. He identified three ways in which leaders change their followers: realizing the importance and value of tasks; Try to focus first on the goals of the team or organization rather than on your

own interests; activate higher needs. In his proposal, charisma is seen as a necessary but not sufficient characteristic of a transformative leader. The lack of charismatic leadership can be attributed to the fact that a charismatic movie star may not be a good leader, although two important charismatic effects that a transformational leader achieves are to evoke strong emotions and to identify employees with leaders. This can be achieved through exciting appeals. This can also be done in a more silent way such as coaching or mentoring.

[8] said that true transformational leadership rests on a moral foundation based on four factors: idealized influence; inspirational motivation; intellectual stimulation; and individualized attention[9]. The three moral dimensions are: the moral character of the leader; the vision, clarity and ethical values embedded in the leader's agenda; the morality of the socio-ethical decision-making and action processes that leaders and followers participate in and jointly enforce [9]. Unlike Burns (1978), he saw transformative leadership as inseparable from higher values, while [8] initially saw a moral value in it and attributed transformational abilities to individuals such as Adolf Hitler and Jim Jones, but opinions changed after the conversation with Burns. [8] made assumptions in his approach to the theory. He believed that recognizing the importance of tasks motivates people and that focusing on a team or organization leads to better work. Various scholars have debated what the most important factors of transformational leadership influence employee performance, and there is no doubt that all factors matter. However, this study focuses on the impact of leadership style on employee engagement. However, this study will focus on leadership style influence on performance.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

A. Review of Variables

This section looks at literature related to the study variables. That is intellectual stimulation, separation of powers, resource allocation, and inspirational motivation.

1) Inspirational Motivation

Inspirational motivation refers to the ability of the leader to motivate the whole organization. Transformational leaders make the followers see an appealing future and offer them opportunities to see meaning in their work. They therefore challenge them with high standards. Such leaders also encourage the followers to be part of organizational culture and environment. Transformational leader possesses the ability to use emotions to motivate their subordinates [10]. This ability could inspire team members towards good mood, and indirectly affect members' satisfaction with their leaders. [11] found out that transformational leadership had a significant direct influence on members' frustration and optimism using the variable of clear and continuous stimulation. While positive moods (optimism) usually evoke higher reported job satisfaction signal a state of satisfaction it is proposed that transformational leaders' inspirational motivation behaviors will positively influence team members' satisfaction with their leaders. The result showed that there was a link between project managers who display inspirational approach and their ability to quickly identify and solve problems with his team.

2) *Idealized behaviors*

Idealized behavior refers to how the leaders build confidence and trust in the followers and also acts as a role model to them [12]. Idealized behaviour has two main components, namely idealized attributes (also called attributed charisma) and idealized [13]. These two components of transformational leadership incorporate the ideas of authors such as [14] and [15] who contributed to the development of the charismatic leadership theory. Typical behaviour associated with idealized attributes includes, instilling pride in those led, going beyond self-interest for the good of the group as a whole, building respect and displaying a sense of power and confidence [14]. [16] conducted a study on switch leadership in Pakistan projects an empirical study reflecting the importance of transformational leadership on project success across twenty eight nations observed that effective project manager leadership is an important success factor on projects [11]. The capabilities of the people involved in resolving conflicts and unforeseen problems are an important key for project success [10]. Effective leadership is a multifaceted process that is often defined through both subjective and objective measures of leader behavior and its effect on project implementation. [17] argue that charismatic leadership is an important aspect of transformational leader, which would result in higher subordinates' satisfaction. [18] assert that, the dimension of charisma was confirmed to be the most important factors to influence members' satisfaction with their leader among four transformational leadership style dimensions.

3) *Individualized Consideration*

Individual consideration is the degree to which the leader attends to each follower needs, acts as a mentor or coach to the follower and listens to their followers concerns and needs Burns (1978). Transformational leaders also tend to be optimistic [19] and more sensitive to subordinates' needs. They provide personal attention to their members through individual consideration. These transformational leadership behaviors could affect team members' satisfaction with the leader. For example, [20] suggested that employees would be more satisfied with project managers who are considerate and supportive than with project managers who are either indifferent or hostile towards subordinates. Transformational leader treats people with dignity and respect through the individualized consideration component of team orientation leadership approach. [21] in their study of Measuring Leadership Styles- a review of project success variables in Netherlands, further explains how transformational leaders trust people and delegate responsibility to assist in getting tasks accomplished in the movement towards goal attainment through the individualized consideration component of individual analysis of followers. Although, [22] look at leadership in Virtual teams, a comparison of transformational and transactional leaders in Yugoslavia explained that Individualized consideration leadership is an aspect of transformational leadership that enhances, increased listening, prompt feedback and openness to suggestions with team members that is necessary for implementation of projects, however they did not address the component of team orientation. Likewise, [23] adds that individual consideration aspect of transformational leadership is indirectly related to empowerment. However there is no empirical evidence that individualized consideration has been specifically linked to project Implementation modulated with conflict resolution strategies. Further [24] observed that transformational leaders can achieve increased effectiveness by harnessing the Pygmalion effect, through individual consideration component of individual analysis of followers.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used descriptive study design which enabled the researcher to generate an accurate profile of factors, events and situations of a study population at a specific point in time to examine the connection between the dependent and independent variables [25]. Descriptive study design enabled the researcher to explain the variables under study and obtain regression models for predicting independent variables [26]. With reference to this study the target population, was all the 338 Deputy County Commissioners (DCCs) in Kenya. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from the DCCs. Questionnaires comprised of both open and closed ended questions assist collect data on the study objectives. Questionnaires helped the researcher gather massive data within a short time [27]. The secondary data is also vital in the study as it assisted the researcher to collect useful information from the library books, annual reports, journals and publications from research institutions. Slovin's formula was used to determine the sample size.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$
$$n = \frac{338}{1 + 338 * 0.05^2}$$
$$n = 183$$

V. RESEARCH FINDINGS

A. Descriptive Statistics of Study Variables

The study computed the descriptive statistics in order to ascertain the whether the objectives are met. Measure of central tendency was used to compute the statistics. The study questionnaire was presented in 5 point Likert scale where 5 (SA) = Strongly Agree, 4(A) = Agree, 3(N) = Neutral, 2 (D) = Disagree, and 1(SD) = Strongly Disagree. Both mean and standard deviation were used to interpret the significance of the statistics. A low standard deviation means the responds had similar opinions while a variation of 2 and above means the responds had varied opinion. The ranges for the response were as follows: 1-1.8 SD; 1.9-.7 D; .8-3.6 N; 3.7-4.3 A; 4.4-5 D. The descriptive statistics of the study variable is as follows

i.) Performance of National Government Administration

The major objective of the study was to examine the influence of Transformational Leadership on Performance of National Government Administration. The study sought to find out the status of performance by looking at the statistics on Table 1 below

TABLE I: PERFORMANCE NATIONAL GOVERNMENT ADMINISTRATION

Statements	Mean	Std. Dev.
This organization has been performing better compared to other Ministries, Departments and Agencies in Government	2.77	1.251
The National Government Administration has improved the quality of its services over time	3.75	1.306
The National Government Administration provide positive feedback in relation to quality of services offered in this organization	3.01	1.091
The National Government Administration has been able to achieve all its goals in time and with stipulated resources	3.00	1.391
Leadership of the National Government Administration inspires employees	3.35	1.232
National Government Administration has provided channels for communication with the general public on issues of service delivery	3.74	1.012
Composite Mean	3.27	1.214

The results show that respondents disagreed that the National Government Administration has a better performance compared to other ministries and government departments indicated by the mean of 2.77. However, the respondents agreed that the National Government Administration has improved the quality of services over time as indicated by the mean of 3.75. The respondents moderately agreed that the National Government Administration provides feedback in relation to the quality of services offered this supported by the mean of 3.01. The respondents also moderately agreed that the National Government Administration has been able to achieve its goals in time and with stipulated resources as shown by the mean of 3.00. The respondents slightly agreed that the leadership of the National Government Administration inspires its employees as indicated by the mean of 3.35. Finally, respondents agreed on the provision of communication channels to the general public on issues of service delivery as indicated by the mean of 3.74. In conclusion, the Composite Mean of 3.27 provided some moderate agreement to suggest that Transformational leadership influences performance of National Government Administration. [10] 'examined transformational leadership style and job satisfaction at higher education institution in Malaysia.' The study targeted 175 'academic staff of Politeknik Sultan Mizan Zainal Abidin'. Intellectual stimulation, charismatic, individualize consideration, and inspirational, leadership styles were found to drive employees' satisfaction. Individualized consideration leadership was also found as the most important leadership in relation to job satisfaction.

ii.) Inspirational Motivation

To determine the influence of Inspirational Motivation on performance of NGA, the study analyzed the following descriptive statistics as show on Table II below present the results.

TABLE II: INSPIRATIONAL MOTIVATION

Statements	Mean	Std. Dev.
The Leadership of the National Government Administration cares about my personal life hence encourages work-life balance	3.34	1.206
The Leadership of the National Government Administration is supportive in development of the strengths of employees	3.82	1.091

The Leadership of the National Government Administration keep us updated on how our actual performance is tracking against plan and targets	3.60	1.391
The Leadership of the National Government Administration challenges that motivate employees to perform in their work / tasks	3.57	1.232
The Leadership of the National Government Administration encourage employees to become part of the overall organizational culture	3.77	1.251
The Leadership of the National Government Administration communicate high expectations that employees want to achieve	3.35	1.125
Composite Mean	3.58	1.216

The findings from Table 4.4 above show that respondents slightly agreed that the leadership of the National Government Administration cares about the personal life of employees and thus encourages work life balance as indicated by the mean of 3.34. Good governance is determined by transformational and accountable leadership that is responsive to the needs and the aspirations of its citizens. The respondents agreed that the National Government Administration is supportive in development of employees' strength as indicated by the mean of 3.82. Capacity building through training of frontline service providers, providing incentives for better performance and accountability may be critical for improved governance and delivery of public services [28]. The study also found moderate agreement by the respondents that the National Government Administration updates employees on actual performance against the planned targets a indicated by the mean of 3.60. Further, the National Government Administration was found to challenge and motivate its employees to perform in their tasks as indicated by the mean of 3.57. The National Government Administration also encourages its employees to be part of the organization culture as shown by the mean of 3.77. Transformational leaders make the followers see an appealing future and offer them opportunities to see meaning in their work. They therefore challenge them with high standards. Such leaders also encourage the followers to be part of organizational culture and environment [29]. Finally, the respondents moderately agreed that the National Government Administration communicates high expectations to be achieved by the employees as indicated by the mean of 3.35. To conclude, the Composite Mean of 3.58 provides some slight significant statistical evidence to suggest that to some extent, Inspirational Motivation influences performance of National Government Administration. The inspiration leader guides the organization from where it is now to the future in three stages: assessing the current status, establishing of goals, and lastly develop techniques to achieve those goals [11].

iii.) Idealized behaviors

The study sought to find out the influence of Idealized Behaviors on Performance of National Government Administration. The findings would be useful in explaining how Idealized Behaviors influences Performance of National Government Administration. The following are the results

TABLE III: IDEALIZED BEHAVIOURS

Statements	Mean	Std. Dev.
National Government Administration combines competencies with organizational goals and objectives	3.15	1.306
The National Government Administration embraces a new way to communication with its employees	3.26	1.091
The National Government Administration encourages proactive behavior among employees.	3.58	1.311
National Government Administration is sensitive to individual employees' needs when making decisions	3.97	1.132
National Government Administration enables decision-making at all levels of the organization	4.78	0.651
National Government Administration sets goals to define what we need to achieved	3.78	1.214
Composite Mean	3.75	1.118

The statistics from Table 4.6 above suggest that respondents agreed slightly that the Leadership of the National Government Administration combines competencies with organizational goals and objectives as shown by the mean of 3.15. The study found slightly that the National Government Administration embraces a new way to communication with its employees as evident by the mean of 3.26. This group of leaders is usually great communicators of inspiring vision to followers. They are competent in communicating their vision to subordinates in ways that they can very easily understand, providing credible

and sufficient information to make possible the attainment of the vision or objectives by subordinates [12]. Further, it slightly found that proactive behavior is encouraged among the employees of the National Government Administration (Mean = 3.58). Respondents agreed that the National Government Administration is sensitive to the needs of employees when making decisions (Mean = 3.97). Transformational leaders with idealized influence or charisma establish a personal relationship with their followers. They constantly and persistently attend to the welfare of employees by being sensitive to their contribution to the planning process (Avolio & Yammarino, 2018)[30]. The outcome of this attention is that the employees develop a greater sense of commitment, engagement or involvement in the organizational processes, and in their jobs (Unpanl, 2017)[31]. There was a strong agreement that decision making is enabled at all the level of the National Government Administration (Mean = 4.78). Finally, respondents agree that goals are set to define what is needed to be achieved (Mean = 3.78). The Composite Mean of 3.75 provided significant statistical evidence to suggest the influence of Idealized Behaviors on Performance of National Government Administration. Idealized influence has been associated with a leader who has charisma, is ethical and one who is able to effectively communicate his/her vision for the organization to subordinates. These leaders manifest strong personal values that set them apart from the rest and establish positive images for their follow [12].

iv.) Individualized Consideration

The study sought to find out the influence of Individualized Consideration on Performance of National Government Administration. The findings would be useful in explaining how Individualized Consideration influences Performance of National Government Administration. The following descriptive statistics in Table IV presents the findings.

TABLE IV: INDIVIDUALIZED CONSIDERATION

Statements	Mean	Std. Dev.
The Leadership of the National Government Administration ensures collaborative decision-making to enhance performance	2.89	1.306
The Leadership of the National Government Administration manages conflicts by handling each situation individually to enhance performance	3.79	1.091
The Leadership of the National Government Administration resolves conflict in a fair ay at the work place	3.62	1.391
The Leadership of the National Government Administration speaks enthusiastically about what it needs to be accomplished	3.98	1.232
The Leadership of the National Government Administration focuses on individual ability rather than group performance	3.77	1.251
The Leadership of the National Government Administration act as coaches in supporting employees to achieve the company’s objectives	3.45	1.234
Composite Mean	3.58	1.251

The descriptive statistics shows that the respondents moderately agreed that the National Government Administration ensures collaborative decision-making to enhance performance as indicated by the mean of 2.89. The respondents also agreed that the Leadership of the National Government Administration manages conflicts by handling each situation individually to enhance performance as indicated by the mean of 3.79. Further, the respondents agree too that conflicts are resolved fairly at the work place as indicated by the mean of 3.62. The Leadership of the National Government Administration also as found to speak enthusiastically about what it needs to be accomplished this is indicated by the mean of 3.98. The study further found that the Leadership of the National Government Administration targets individual ability rather than group performance as indicated by the mean of 3.77. Finally, the respondents had some slight agreement that the leadership of the Leadership of the National Government Administration act like coaches to support employees in achieving the objectives of the organization (Mean = 3.45). In conclusion, the Composite Mean of 3.58 provided some significant evidence to suggest Individualized Consideration to some extent influences performance of the National Government Administration. Individual consideration leader tends to be optimists and are sensitive to the needs of subordinates and as well provide attention to the team members. They treat people with dignity and respect. They trust people and delegate responsibilities in order to assist in getting tasks accomplished in attainment of goals. These leaders have the willingness to stimulating and creating learning experiences to their followers through delegations and treating each individual uniquely. These leaders have the accountability and capability to offer enhance the productivity of followers

and their satisfaction through assistance, support job development, and being pleasant to their followers. Individual consideration ensures there is a sense of responsibility by providing leaning ability while still supporting the followers individually. They have attention to desire of their followers by making them feel appreciated and treated differently but fairly on an individual basis [10].

B. Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics were used to assess the association between dependent and independent variables. Inferential statistics computed in this study was correlation analysis and regression analysis.

i.) Correlation Analysis

Pearson R correlation was used to measure strength and the direction of linear relationship between variables. The association was considered to be: small if $\pm 0.1 < r < \pm 0.29$; medium if $\pm 0.3 < r < \pm 0.49$; and strong if $r > \pm 0.5$. Table 4.8 below shows the results.

TABLE V: CORRELATION MATRIX

	Performance of NGA	Inspirational Motivation	Idealized Behaviours	Individualized Consideration
Performance of NGA	1	.811*	.517*	.566**
Pearson Correlation				
Sig. (2-Tailed)		.017	.035	.004
N		138	138	138

** . Correlation Is Significant At The 0.01 Level (2-Tailed).

*. Correlation Is Significant At The 0.05 Level (2-Tailed).

The findings in Table V show that Inspirational Motivation and Performance of National Government Administration have a strong positive and significant relationship ($r=0.811$, $p=0.017$). Since the p-value was less than the selected level of significance, the relationship was considered to be significant. The study also shows a very strong association between Inspirational Motivation and Performance of National Government Administration. Further, there is a direct relationship between the Inspirational Motivation and Performance of National Government Administration meaning an increase in Inspirational Motivation will lead to an increase in Performance of National Government Administration. The relationship between Idealized Behaviours and Performance of National Government Administration was also found to be strong ($r=0.517$). Since the p-value (0.035) was less than the selected level of significance (0.05), the relationship was considered to be significant. The study found a direct relationship between the Idealized Behaviours and Performance of National Government Administration meaning an increase in Idealized Behaviours will lead to an increase in Performance of National Government Administration. Finally, Individualized Consideration is seen to have strong positive and significant relationship with Performance of National Government Administration ($r=0.566$, $p=0.004$). The p-value was less than the selected level of significance (0.05) suggesting the relationship was significant. Individualized Consideration has a direct relationship with Performance of National Government Administration meaning an increase in Individualized Consideration will lead to an increase in Performance of National Government Administration. These findings suggest that there was significant relationship between the independent variables (Inspirational Motivation, Idealized behaviours, and Individualized Consideration) and the dependent variable (Performance of National Government Administration). The findings concur with the finding of [12] that Inspirational Motivation, , Idealized behaviors, and Individualized Consideration have significant and positive influence on performance of employees of NGOs in Kenya. In a study by Breynha and Damoah (2016) on strategic leadership styles and employee engagement in the telecommunication sector in Ghana, established that individualized consideration, inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation have positive effect and correlation with employee engagement except idealized influence that has an insignificant relationship.”

ii.) Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

ANOVA was done to establish the significance and fitness of the model. The assumption of ANOVA is that the p-value has to be less than the accepted threshold of 0.05 for the study to be significant and fit in estimating the implementation of the project. Table VI below shows the results.

TABLE VI: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	40.330	4	10.083	13.197	.000 ^b
Residual	101.578	133	0.764		
Total	141.908	137			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of National Government Administration

b. Predictors: (Constant), Inspirational Motivation, Idealized behaviors, Individualized Consideration

The results in VI indicate that the model was significant since the p-value (0.000) was less than 0.05 thus the model is statistical significance in establishing the influence of Inspirational Motivation, Idealized behaviors, Individualized Consideration on Performance of National Government Administration. Further, the F-Statistics (4, 133) = 13.197 (8.640) is greater than the F-critical (4, 133) = 2.439 suggesting the significance of the model. Thus, at least one of the Variables in: Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, Idealized behaviors, and Individualized Consideration is fit in explaining change of performance at the National Government Administration in Kenya.

iii.) Model Summary

From the findings in Table VII below, the value of adjusted R square was 0.691 which suggests that 69.1% variation in Performance of National Government Administration can be explained by changes in Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, Idealized behaviors, and Individualized Consideration. The remaining 30.9% suggests that other factors can be attributed to variation in leadership style factors that were not discussed in this study. The correlation coefficient (R) shows the relationship strength between the study variables.

TABLE VII: MODEL SUMMARY

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.833 ^a	.694	.691	.82018

a. Predictors: (Constant) Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, Idealized behaviors, Individualized Consideration

iv.) Regression Analysis

Regression analysis was done to identify the value of the dependent variable when the independent variables changes. The Beta coefficients are significant if the p-value is less than the threshold of 0.05. Table VIII below shows that all the p-values are less than the accepted threshold of 0.05.

TABLE VIII: COEFFICIENTS FOR REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.362	0.135		10.089	0.000
1 Inspirational Motivation	0.453	0.173	0.590	2.618	0.017
Idealized behaviors	0.205	0.079	0.280	2.594	0.015
Individualized Consideration	0.313	0.091	0.404	3.439	0.005

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of National Government Administration

$$SD = 1.362 + 0.7453IM + 0.205IB + 0.313IC + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots (ii)$$

The model equation above reveals that holding the variables Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, Idealized behaviors and Individualized Consideration will be at a constant value of 1.362. The results reveal that Inspirational Motivation has a significant influence on perormance of NGA P-value 0.017 < 0.05. The variable also has highest influence (standardized beta = 0.590) on performance of NGA. An increase in Inspirational Motivation will lead to 45.3% increase in performance of NGA. The study also found Idealized behaviors to have a significant influence on performance of NGA where P-value 0.015 < 0.05. The variable also influences performance of NGA by 0.280 or 28% (standardized beta = 0.280). Thus, for an increase in Idealized behaviors increases performance of NGA by 28%. The variable also has the third highest influence on performance of NGA. Individualized Consideration has significant influence on performance of NGA where

P-value $0.005 < 0.05$. The variable also influences performance of NGA by 0.313 or 31.3% (standardized beta = 0.404). Thus for an increase in Individualized Consideration increases performance of NGA by 40.4%. The variable also has the second highest influence on performance of NGA. In conclusion, Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, Idealized behaviors, and Individualized Consideration a factors of Transformation leadership significantly influence performance of National Government Administration. [12] in her study on the influence of Transformational leadership on employee performance of Non-Governmental organizations in Kenya, found Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, Idealized influence, and Individualized Consideration to influence employee performance

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The study sought to examine how Transformational Leadership influences performance of National Government Administration. The overarching objective of public provision of free or subsidized services in low income countries is to deliver social protection to the poor and vulnerable and to alleviate poverty. The quality of leadership, thus, has direct implications for economic growth. The first research objective was to determine the influence of Inspirational Motivation on performance of National Government Administration.. The study established that a unit increase in Inspirational Motivation increased performance of National Government Administration. The study further established a significant correlation between Inspirational Motivation and performance of National Government Administration. The study also found that the relationship was positive and slightly strong. Based on the study findings, the study concludes that there is significant influence of Inspirational Motivation performance of National Government Administration. The second research objective was to determine the influence of Idealized Behaviors on performance of National Government Administration. The study found that Idealized Behaviors has significant positive and slightly strong influence on performance of National Government Administration. The study also found that Idealized Behaviors was significant. From these findings, the study concludes that there is significant influence of Idealized Behaviors on performance of National Government Administration. The third objective was to determine the influence of Individualized Consideration on performance of National Government Administration. The study found that a unit increase in Individualized Consideration increased on performance of National Government Administration. There was a positive significant and slightly strong correlation between Individualized Consideration and performance of National Government Administration. From the study findings, the study concludes that there is a significant influence of Individualized Consideration on performance of National Government Administration.

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